

VISCOELASTIC INTER-PLY SLIP IN UNCURED LAMINATES: EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERISATION AND MODELLING

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the inter-ply shear behaviour of uncured carbon fibre prepreg is fundamental to avoiding process-induced defects during manufacturing of large-scale components. Shear tests for AS4/8552 are compared to a one-dimensional viscoelastic-plastic model for inter-ply shear. The paper utilises a proven methodology to derive key parameters from which an insight into the effects of angled interfaces can be gained. Investigation of angled ply interfaces shows a significant impact on the shear behaviour; increasing interface angle increases the initial stiffness whilst reducing the post yield hardening. The mechanisms thought to control this behaviour are discussed in depth, along with simple application to industrial scenarios and more complex process modelling.

1 INTRODUCTION

Whilst the basic advantages of composite materials are well proven, they are often compromised by high costs, long development time, and poor quality due to manufacturing defects. This is particularly noticeable in the complex structures found in large aerospace applications. If laminates are to conform to a surface with curvature during forming or consolidation, plies within a laminate must shear relative to one another. If plies are prevented from shearing the process becomes susceptible to generating a host of manufacturing induced defects including ply wrinkling [1-4] (e.g. Fig. 1), part distortion [5-7] and poor consolidation [8]. To limit the formation of such defects, the characterisation of shear properties of materials is vital to not only determine optimal shear conditions for manufacturability, but to provide input parameters for process simulations [3] and manufacturing design methods [9].

In [10] an experimental program is developed to characterise inter-ply shear. Data collected from this program can be fed into the viscoelasto-plastic model developed alongside it to provide key modelling parameters for novel process modelling techniques. A key aspect of this work is that it considers rate of deformation. This allows for an accurate portrayal of the resin as a viscoelastic material. In its uncured state the resin plays a complex part in the overall material behaviour. One vital limitation of this work is that it only considers interfaces between layers with fibres aligned in the direction of shear deformation (0-0° interfaces), whilst real laminates contain a range of differently angled plies. The main objective of this paper is to utilise this model to investigate the influence of differently angled ply interfaces.

Figure 1. CT image of a typical wrinkle defect in a corner, arising due to the inability of layers to slip over one another

After a description of the experimental setup and some initial observations of the resulting load traces (Section 2), we describe in brief the one-dimensional viscoelastic-plastic model (Section 3) developed in [10]. Using this model we then discuss key parameters drawn from experimental data (Section 4) in order to better understand the influence of angle ply interfaces. These parameters provide simple metrics by which to compare through thickness shear properties (Section 5), for different interfaces. In Section 6 we consider two different manufacturing scenarios, forming and consolidation over corner radius. Whilst previous work [11] suggests optimum manufacturing conditions independent of manufacturing process, the parameterised model presented in [10] suggests process dependent manufacturing conditions (temperature and rate) for optimal manufacturability in forming and consolidation scenarios. The paper concludes with a summary of the key findings, and possible future avenues of research.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

2.1 Experimental procedure, material and sample preparation

Figure 2 (Left), shows a schematic of the test rig which consisted of two independent components. Firstly, a lock-able hinged array connected to an Instron load cell at (i), consisted of a pneumatic cylinder (ii) which pulled together two plates (area, $A = 50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$) wrapped in a single layer of carbon fibre prepreg (iii). These plates clamped either side of a central plate (iv), also wrapped in a layer of carbon fibre prepreg, which was fixed to the bottom mounting of an Instron testing machine (v). The rig was mounted within an environmental chamber, allowing the temperature of test to be controlled. The test procedure was as follows: (1) test temperature was achieved in the environmental chamber; (2) the pressure in the pneumatic cylinder was controlled to generate a normal clamping stress σ_n between the side and central plates (3) the Instron pulled the upper part of the rig at a constant rate $R = du/dt$, whilst the load cell recorded the force F . All experiments were carried out using AS4/8552 (of ply thickness $h/2 = 0.25 \text{ mm}$), wrapped around each plate so that the fibres were oriented vertically. The angled interface was achieved by rotation of the two smaller plates, whilst the ply alignment around the central plate remained at 0° . Tests were conducted at a range of angles, φ , and temperatures. Rate of deformation was set to $R = 0.1 \text{ mm/min}$ and normal pressure was kept at $\sigma_n = 75 \text{ kPa}$. The set of tests carried out are summarised in Section 4, Table 1.

Figure 2. (Left) Schematic of interply test rig in which the two individual parts move apart at a constant rate R and the required force is recorded. (Right) Stress-strain traces for shear tests at 70, 80 and 90°C and rate $R = 0.1\text{mm/min}$ and $\sigma_n = 75\text{kPa}$.

Before carrying out these tests it was necessary to calibrate the rig for a material with a known coefficient of friction. A number of tests were carried out using PTFE instead of CFRP; giving an average value of $\mu = 0.096$, which was within the documented range of 0.05-0.10 [12]. A number of operational caveats were noted, as explained in [10].

2.2 Comparison of initial experimental results with existing literature

Figure 2 (Right) shows 3 typical load traces obtained from the shear tests. Each trace shows a similar response to those displayed by Larberg et al. [13], whereby each plot has two distinct regions. The first region, characterized by an initial stiffness, can be attributed to the shear behaviour of the two plies at small strains, before the interface yields. This is followed by a second region once the interface yields, at a reduced stiffness. The key characteristics of the preliminary results can be summarised as follows:

- (1) The initial stiffness is dependent on both rate and temperature, but is independent of pressure;
- (2) The point of yield, i.e. the transition between the two regions of behaviour is dependent on both temperature and pressure;
- (3) The post yield stiffness (or hardening) is dependent on rate and temperature.

In [10] a one-dimensional viscoelastic-plastic model is introduced, which captures the behaviour observed in these preliminary results. This simplified heuristic model is used to condense the set of complex experimental results into a small set of key parameters, yet retains the fundamental mechanics observed. This model and the set of parameters provide simple metrics by which to compare through thickness shear properties for different materials and manufacturing conditions (e.g. temperature, pressure or rate, see Section 4). Furthermore, such data provides vital input for process models, see for example [3, 4].

3 ONE DIMENSIONAL VISCOELASTO-PLASTIC MODEL FOR INTER-PLY SHEAR

The full derivation of this model and the parameters drawn from it is discussed in [10], however the highlights shall be presented here. As discussed in Section 2 a typical stress-strain trace for an interply shear test can be broken down into two distinct regions, pre and post yield (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. The bi-linear stress-strain response for the visco-elasto plastic model overlays a typical experimental load trace for fixed temperature $T = 70^\circ\text{C}$, normal pressure $\sigma_n = 75\text{kPa}$ and strain rate $d\gamma/dt = 3.33\text{e-}3\text{s}^{-1}$. The plot is characterised by two lines, which describe the shear response pre and post-yield

Pre-yield behaviour is decomposed into rate dependent and independent parts. A constitutive law with these characteristics is given by the relationship

$$\tau = \left(G + \eta \frac{d\gamma}{dt} \right) \gamma = K\gamma \quad (1)$$

where G is rate independent shear stiffness, η the coefficient of viscosity, γ is the shear strain du/h and $d\gamma/dt$ the strain rate. The parameter K denotes the overall initial rate dependent stiffness.

The onset of inter-ply slip, τ_c , is defined by a Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion

$$\tau_c = \mu\sigma_n + j \quad (2)$$

such that μ is the coefficient of friction, σ_n is the normal stress and j a measure of joint strength.

The incremental post yield response is given by

$$\Delta\tau = K_t\Delta\gamma = K \left(1 - \frac{K}{K+H} \right) \Delta\gamma \quad (3)$$

where K_t is termed the consistent tangent stiffness, and H the strain hardening parameter.

The effects of angled interfaces shall be investigated by comparing the values of K and K_t over a range of interface angles.

4 RESULTS

Figure 4 (Left) shows pre-yield stiffness K against interface angle φ at 40°C. The test response shows an initially rapid increase in K with changing φ with the response plateauing as φ approaches 45°. Figure 4 (Right) shows consistent tangent stiffness K_t against interface angle φ at 40°C. The test response shows an initially rapid decrease in K_t with changing φ with the response again plateauing as φ approaches 45°.

Figure 4. (Left) Initial shear stiffness K against interface angle φ . (Right) Consistent tangent stiffness K_t against interface angle φ . Tests were conducted at a temperature of 40°C, rate $R = 0.1\text{mm/min}$ and normal pressure $\sigma_n = 75\text{kPa}$.

Figure 5 shows consistent tangent stiffness K_t against temperature at $\varphi = 10^\circ$. The results show an increase in K_t to a maximum at 60°C before decreasing as the temperature increases further.

Figure 5. Consistent tangent stiffness K_t against temperature. Tests were conducted at $\varphi = 10^\circ$, rate $R = 0.1\text{mm/min}$ and normal pressure $\sigma_n = 75\text{kPa}$

The derived values of K and K_t for each test run are given in Table 1. The dashes denote tests that were not run.

Angle φ	Temperature (°C)											
	40			60			70			90		
	K	K_t	τ_c	K	K_t	τ_c	K	K_t	τ_c	K	K_t	τ_c
	(kPa)			(kPa)			(kPa)			(kPa)		
0	81.2	1.47	6.15	64.6	3.86	3.68	62.2	3.88	2.85	54.8	1.27	1.89
5	85.5	1.41	6.05	-	-	-	68.6	3.23	2.83	-	-	-
10	90.0	1.32	6.29	74.3	3.09	3.65	69.2	2.81	2.79	59.1	0.99	1.83
20	93.9	1.24	6.49	78.2	2.50	3.35	-	-	-	62.4	0.84	1.82
45	96.0	1.17	6.37	83.2	2.13	3.28	80.6	2.14	2.92	-	-	-

Table 1: Table of K , K_t and τ_c for all values of temperature and interface angle φ tested. All tests were conducted at a rate of deformation $R = 0.1\text{mm/min}$ and normal pressure $\sigma_n = 75\text{kPa}$.

5 DISCUSSION

Figure 4 (Left) shows an increase in initial shear stiffness K by up to 19% as the interface angle increases towards $\varphi = 45^\circ$. Work done in [10] suggests that K is highly dependent upon the resin interface between the two plies. It is also suggested that the stiffness of this region is influenced to a varying degree by the presence of the fibrous reinforcement. The behaviour shown in Fig. 4 is therefore thought to be due to the way in which the fibres transfer load into the resin. It is thought that with a $0-0^\circ$ interface the fibres are able to slip or flow through the resin with little difficulty, as the fibres are aligned in the direction of loading. In this case the resin does not have to redistribute, (Fig. 6 (Left)), as the fibres are simply being pulled through a bed of resin, and permanent channels exist between fibres (Fig. 7 (Left)). These channels do not exist for angled interfaces however. As the fibres become more and more misaligned from one ply to the next, they are instead dragged width ways through the resin (Fig. 6 (Right)). This requires the redistribution of resin around the fibres as they move, offering significantly more resistance to slip and therefore effectively stiffening up the interface.

Figure 6. Showing direction of fibre movement with the solid line and resulting resin movement with the dashed for (Left) a 0° fibre and (Right) a 45° fibre

In the case of the post yield consistent tangent stiffness K_t , Fig. 4 (Right) displays a loss in stiffness with increasing angle φ , with a 21% reduction in stiffness when comparing a $0-45^\circ$ interface to a $0-0^\circ$. Work from [10] suggests that the post yield region is influenced by the level of fibre-fibre contact between plies. As such, it is suggested that the observed decrease in K_t seen in Fig. 4 (Right) is due to fibre packing. As shown in Fig. 7 (Left), a $0-0^\circ$ interface provides optimum packing density, and therefore the greatest degree of fibre-fibre contact. Even a slight misalignment between plies will drastically reduce the amount of fibre-fibre contact (Fig. 7 (Right)), resulting in the sharp decrease in stiffness observed in Fig. 4 (Right). Another theory proposed in [10] was that reforming of the joint could occur when the resin was free to flow. If the flow of resin is hindered by angled interfaces, as

suggested earlier, this could prevent joint reformation, promoting the physical dislocation of ply interfaces which was considered to lower post-yield stiffness in [10].

Figure 7. (Left) showing packing of fibres at a 0-0 interface and (Right) at a 0-45 interface,

Observing the values of K_t plotted in Figure 5 we see peaked behaviour with increasing temperature, with K_t being initially fairly low at 40°C before reaching a maximum at 70°C and falling again as the temperature approaches 90°C. This is in keeping with findings in [10] when plotting the strain hardening parameter, H , against temperature. It was suggested that this behaviour is due to the viscosity of the resin allowing some flow at the interface. Whilst the new results confirm the behavioural pattern they do little to help explain it, as H for the tests cannot be calculated without a complete set of data at varying rates for each angle.

The values of critical shear stress, τ_c , shown in Table 1 indicate a very slight increase in τ_c at 40 and 70°C, and a very slight decrease in τ_c at 60 and 90°C. It is therefore suggested that the variance in τ_c values is simple due to the level of repeatability of the tests. Work in [10] noted τ_c to be the least repeatable value, due in part to the fact that it was dependent on the accurate control of both rate and pressure, whereas most other variables are independent of one or the other. As such, initial tests suggest interface angle has a negligible influence on τ_c , which holds with the observations in [10], describing τ_c as the yield point, i.e. the point at which slip occurs in the resin rich area between plies. Angled plies should not influence the critical stress in this resin rich zone, according to the earlier hypothesis they simply affect how load is transferred into it.

5.1 Inter-ply slip in laminate shear

Up to this point the discussion and results presented appear to suggest that both the pre-yield shear and post yield slip behaviour localise at the ply interface. However, shear strains and strain rates are all calculated relative to ply thicknesses, rather than to the thickness of the interface. The principal reasoning behind this is that the characterisation has been designed with laminate behaviour in mind (see Section 6). Laminate shear is considered as two shear springs in series, of which one spring is the interface region and one spring the fibrous region with shear modulus denoted here as S , where S is equivalent to K and K_t of Eqs. (1) and (3). From [14] we see that $h_{fib.} \approx 16h_{int.}$ and $S_{fib.} \approx 1000S_{int.}$, thus

$$\frac{h}{S} = \frac{h_{int.}}{S_{int.}} + \frac{h_{fib.}}{S_{fib.}} \approx \frac{h_{int.}}{S_{int.}} \left(1 + \frac{16}{1000} \right) \quad (4)$$

where $h = h_{int.} + h_{fib.}$. From this equation we can see that the contribution to laminate shear from the fibrous region is negligible, and as such

$$S = \frac{S_{int} \cdot h}{h_{int}} \quad (5)$$

The laminate shear stiffness S is therefore an approximation of the shear behaviour of the ply as a result of localised shear or slip at the interface between the constituent layers. If we were to consider shear behaviour on a ply level, we would simply change the strain based on the h ratio from [14]. For this work we consider laminate shear as it is better suited to our application (see Section 6), that is to say, we are more interested in the macro-scale defect than the micro-scale mechanism.

5.2 Symmetrical angles

Whilst symmetrical interface angles were not investigated, it seems reasonable to assume that the results for these angles should be identical, as the test setup is simply mirrored. As such, Fig. 8 displays K_t with the assumption of symmetry. This symmetry would also suggest a minimum value of K_t at $\varphi = 90^\circ$, as the physical tests for 89° and 91° would be identical.

Figure 8. Consistent tangent stiffness K_t (kPa) versus angle φ assuming data to be equivalent for symmetric angles. Tests conducted at 40°C , rate $R = 0.1\text{mm/min}$ and normal pressure $\sigma_n = 75\text{kPa}$.

Initial testing of angles greater than $\varphi = 45^\circ$ proved difficult as problems arose with the integrity of the ply on the central plate. This was due to the unconstrained vertical edges on the test samples leading to the ply pulling apart rather than shear as a single body. In a real component this is not a problem, as the quantity of surrounding material and overall debulk pressure prevents this from occurring. A solution has since been developed by which a selective cure is applied to the edges of the central ply using an electrical circuit, with weights to simulate autoclave pressure. This is coupled with a cooling plate used to keep the centre of the ply at room temperature and contain the cure to a region outside of the desired testing area. As such, the plies are unable to split at the edges and initial results have shown good results for greater angles which will be investigated in greater detail in the future.

5.3 Frictional contact at the interface

As discussed earlier, work in [10] suggests post yield behaviour to be dominated by frictional contact between plies at the fibre interface. As shown in Fig. 7 (Left), maximum contact occurs in the $0-0^\circ$ scenario, with perfect line contact between the fibres. If the fibres are assumed to be rigid bodies, as shown in Fig. 7 (Right), even a small degree of misorientation will break this line contact and result in spot contact, due to the relatively small diameter of the fibres when compared with their length. As such, frictional contact would be reliant upon the number of spot contacts. However, this would

suggest that frictional contact, and therefore resistance to slip, would increase with φ between $0 < \varphi \leq 90^\circ$, contrary to Fig. 4 (Right).

Considering the fibres instead as flexible beams we no longer have spot contact, rather a reducing amount of line contact as $\varphi \rightarrow 90^\circ$. The amount of contact depends upon the geodesic section of the fibre bed at various values of φ , as shown in Fig. 9, the bending stiffness of the fibres and the level of overburden pressure applied to the plies [15]. Future work will focus on adapting the methodology presented in [15] such that it is suitable for use in a CFRP laminate scenario in order to be able to accurately predict the degree of frictional contact a various interface angles.

Figure 9. Showing the differing amount of line contact arising from a flexible fibre draped over two cylindrical fibres when (Left) $\varphi = 90^\circ$ and (Right) φ is some angle $0 < \varphi < 90^\circ$. The dashed line boxes show the section of the fibre bed being viewed.

6 APPLICATION

A simple application of the research has been to predict the optimum forming parameters for different manufacturing processes. By understanding the geometry of the part and forming process employed it is possible to calculate the shear strain required for the part to conform to the required geometry; minimising the likelihood of manufacturing defects (see for example the out-of-plane wrinkles shown in Fig. 1). If we now consider two different forming approaches we can understand the difference in shear strain required for defect free forming. First we consider a debulk scenario (Fig. 10) (Left), such as might occur after deposition of plies around a radius.

Figure 10. (Left) Consolidation of a composite laminate over one half of a symmetrical semi-circular tool. (Right) Drape forming of a composite laminate over the same tool. δs is the total slip. Due to symmetry the right edge of laminate is effectively fixed horizontally.

For this example the slip can be calculated as the difference between the outer arc length before and after debulk. The pre-debulk arc length,

$$s_{\text{pre}} = \left(r + \frac{1}{2}(Nh) \right) \theta \quad (6)$$

where r is tool radius, N is number of plies, θ is tool angle and $h/2$ is ply thickness. The post-debulk arc length,

$$s_{\text{post}} = \left(r - \frac{1}{2}((1 - \alpha)Nh) \right) \quad (7)$$

where α is the percentage consolidation. Therefore for the consolidation scenario, the required shear strain is

$$\gamma_{\text{cons.}} = \ln \left(1 + \frac{s_{\text{pre}} - s_{\text{post}}}{\frac{1}{2}(Nh)} \right) = \ln((1 - \alpha)\theta). \quad (8)$$

Figure 10 (Right) relates to a drape forming scenario in which a laminate is laid flat then formed to a geometric tool. For this example the inter-ply slip is the difference in length between the arc length at the outer radius,

$$s_{\text{post}} = \theta \left(r - \frac{1}{2}(Nh) \right) \quad (9)$$

and the length of the laminate,

$$s_{\text{pre}} = \theta r \quad (10)$$

Thus,

$$\gamma_{\text{form}} = \ln \left(1 + \frac{s_{\text{post}} - s_{\text{pre}}}{\frac{1}{2}(Nh)} \right) = \ln(1 + \theta). \quad (11)$$

Interestingly the shear strain generated is dependent on the angle of the corner radius θ , and for the consolidation case the amount of consolidation. If we consider $\theta = \pi/2$ and the level of consolidation is $\alpha = 12\%$ [3, 8], we can therefore see that the corner consolidation example generates a shear strain of $\gamma = 0.32$, whilst the drape forming scenario requires a much greater shear strain of $\gamma = 0.94$.

By consulting the material specific load traces it is then possible to determine which combination of temperature, pressure and rate of deformation will result in the lowest shear stress to achieve that particular shear strain. In Fig. 10 (Left) the shear strain required to consolidate the part is 0.32. At strains this low the key variables are the initial stiffness, K , and the critical shear stress, τ_c . For example in Fig. 3 these two parameters account for $\approx 81\%$ of the shear stress at a shear strain of 0.32. From test data the lowest K value is obtained at a temperature of 90°C when $\varphi = 0^\circ$, with τ_c also minimising at this temperature.

The scenario displayed in Fig. 10 (Right) induces a much higher shear strain of 0.94, meaning post yield behaviour has a much larger influence on the shear stress values of interest. In this instance we are looking to minimise both K and τ_c . From the data we can see that τ_c is lowest at 90°C , and that K is minimised at this temperature when $\varphi = 45^\circ$

In both these scenarios wrinkling occurs as a result of end-loading of the fibres when plies are not able to slip over one another. Whilst minimising resistance to inter-ply movement reduces this end-

load, it also results in the plies acting as individual layers. As such they are inherently more susceptible to buckling than when the interface is so stiff as to make the plies act as a single laminate. Thus in order to effectively use this data to predict optimum forming regimes, a thorough understanding of the process itself is required.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The test methodology and modelling techniques developed in [10] have successfully been used to investigate a range of angled ply scenarios. The effects of angled interfaces are significant, with a change of ~20% between values of K and K_i from a 0-0° interface to a 0-45°. The results of these tests have given some insight into the effects of an angled interface within a laminate suggesting that dissimilar angles are desirable at the interface for large strain situations, but detrimental to small strain scenarios. Importantly for the former case, increasing the angle does not increase τ_c , making control of the interface angle very effective in combatting post yield hardening. This could influence the degree to which ply blocking is utilised in the design of the laminate. Work on angle optimisation for structural efficiency has already shown that non-standard angles (such as 20° and 70° rather than 0° and 45°) might provide improved damage tolerance, [16], contrary to the perception in current design rules. As such, a similar optimisation approach could potentially be employed to determine the optimal laminate stacking sequence and angles of plies for various forming scenarios such as those discussed above, as even a small mismatch in interface angle can dramatically improve formability. It should be noted however that temperature remains the key parameter when considering optimum forming parameters.

The main impact of this research is therefore its potential to influence laminate stacking sequence design. Prior to this work the output was predominantly focused on controlling the forming and manufacturing parameters, such as temperature and debulk pressure. This angled ply work now allows an insight into how the actual structure of the laminate can be manipulated in order to minimize the occurrence of defects.

An area of further interest is the investigation of combined load scenarios, in particular the bending and shearing of an uncured laminate. This process results in significant amounts of shear within a layered structure. Work on this process is presented in [14], where a laminate beam of 0° plies is tested using a dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMA) rig. This work utilises parameters drawn from the model presented in this paper, and with the new angled interface results it will be possible to investigate more realistic laminates.

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